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FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG REGULAR LGU EMPLOYEES IN KAWAYAN, BILIRAN

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ABSTRACT

Jhes Ann Callao, Wilson Corpin, Joe Paul Nadores, Fatimajen Saberon, Biliran Province State University, Naval, Biliran, Philippines. April 2025. **"FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG REGULAR LGU EMPLOYEES IN KAWAYAN, BILIRAN"** An Undergraduate Thesis.

Adviser: **JAMES V. LAMBIT**

Abstract

This study examined the financial literacy of regular Local Government Unit (LGU) employees in Kawayan, Biliran, focusing on the influence of demographic factors such as age, sex, educational attainment, years of service, and monthly income. Employing a convergent parallel mixed methods design, the research combined quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding of financial literacy. The findings revealed that while employees demonstrated moderate levels of financial literacy, significant variations were observed when grouped according to demographic characteristics. The integration of quantitative results with qualitative narratives showed convergence. While employees valued saving and understood its importance, financial constraints and rising living costs prevented them from translating positive attitudes into consistent behavior. The study underscores the importance of enhancing financial education programs for LGU employees to strengthen the researcher's capacity in managing resources effectively. It concludes that improving financial literacy is vital not only for personal well-being but also for promoting financial responsibility and stability among government employees, thereby contributing to more efficient public service.

Keywords: *demographic factors, financial attitude, financial behavior, financial knowledge, financial literacy, Kawayan, LGU employee*

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INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Financial literacy serves as an essential foundation for personal and national economic stability (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). It refers to the ability of individuals to understand and effectively use financial knowledge, skills, and tools to make informed decisions regarding budgeting, saving, investing, and debt management (Lusardi & Tufano, 2015).

In the Philippine context, financial literacy remains a national concern. A report from the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) revealed that only one-fourth of Filipino adults answered basic financial literacy questions correctly, indicating the need for more targeted educational initiatives (Business Mirror, 2022). This situation is particularly relevant to employees in the public sector, where responsible financial management is expected both professionally and personally.

Regular employees of Local Government Units (LGUs) hold positions that directly influence service delivery, budgeting, and community development. Despite this professional exposure to financial processes, many public servants continue to face economic difficulties. Limited income, high living costs, and inadequate access to financial education hinder their ability to apply financial knowledge in practical contexts (Potrich, Vieira, & Kirch, 2015). The present study focuses on the financial literacy of regular LGU employees in the Municipality of Kawayan, Biliran, to determine the extent of financial knowledge, attitude, and behavior among public workers.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to investigate the of financial literacy among regular LGU employees. Specifically, the research sought;

1. To analyze the impact of demographic profile:
 - 1.1 age,
 - 1.2 educational attainment,
 - 1.3 sex,
 - 1.4 years of service, and
 - 1.5 monthly income.
2. To assess the regular LGU employee's financial literacy in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 financial knowledge,
 - 2.2 financial attitude, and
 - 2.3 financial behavior.
3. Explore the challenges on financial literacy of regular LGU Employees.
4. Design an intervention plan relevant to financial literacy.

Framework of the Study

This section presents the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study.

Theoretical Framework

Financial literacy theory explains that understanding financial concepts like budgeting and investing does not always lead to effective financial behavior, highlighting the need for practical application (OECD, 2013; Salise & Batobalani, 2024).

Behavioral finance theory shows that psychological factors and cognitive biases influence financial decisions, with confidence and demographic differences affecting financial behavior (Kahneman & Tversky, 2009; Chen & Volpe, 2008).

Adult learning theory emphasizes that adults learn best through experience and real-world application, making hands-on financial training more effective for LGU employees (Knowles, Holton, & Swanson, 2015).

Overall, the framework suggests a multifaceted approach that integrates psychological, demographic, and educational factors to enhance the financial literacy and decision-making of LGU employees.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework: Input-Process-Output (IPO) Model

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METHODOLOGY

This presents the research design, locale, respondents, and instruments used to examine financial literacy among regular LGU employees in Kawayan, Biliran.

Research Design

The study employed a **convergent parallel mixed-methods design**, combining surveys and interviews to assess the financial literacy of LGU employees, thereby allowing quantitative results to be validated and enriched by qualitative insights (Dewasiri et al., 2018).

Research Locale

The study took place in **Kawayan, Biliran**, a fifth-class municipality in Eastern Visayas with about 20,455 residents, providing an appropriate setting to assess the financial literacy of employees whose financial practices impact local community welfare.

Research Respondents

The participants consisted of all seventy-eight (78) regular LGU employees in Kawayan, Biliran. For the qualitative phase, fifteen (15) participants were selected through purposive sampling based on employment tenure, income bracket, and age group.

Research Instrument

A **validated questionnaire** adapted from Agustin et al. (2023) with four sections: demographics, financial knowledge, attitude, and behavior, was used alongside semi-structured interviews, with a **Krippendorff's Alpha of 0.82** confirming high reliability.

Data Gathering Procedure and Data Analysis

Formal approval was obtained from Biliran Province State University and the Municipal Mayor of Kawayan prior to data collection. After receiving authorization, the researchers distributed the questionnaires personally to the participants, explaining each item to ensure understanding. Completed questionnaires were retrieved on the same day. Interviews were conducted afterward to collect qualitative information that could contextualize quantitative findings. All responses were treated confidentially and stored securely.

The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. A weighted mean scale determined the overall level of financial literacy: 4.21–5.00 (Strongly Agree), 3.41–4.20 (Agree), 2.61–3.40 (Neutral), 1.81–2.60 (Disagree), and 1.00–1.80 (Strongly Disagree). The qualitative data were analyzed through Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis, which involved coding, theme identification, and interpretation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This includes the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data based on the study's objectives.

Table 1

Demographic Profile

Age	f	%
21-30 years old	8	10.26
31-40 years old	46	58.97
41-50 years old	15	19.23
51 years old and above	9	11.54
Total	78	100

The demographic data revealed that a majority of the participants (58.97%) belonged to the age group of 31–40 years, indicating a mid-career workforce.

Table 2

Sex

Sex	f	%
Female	41	52.56
Male	37	47.44
TOTAL	78	100

Female employees represented 52.56% of the sample, while male employees accounted for 47.44%.

Table 3

Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	f	%
College Graduate	63	80.77
College Level	7	8.97
High School Graduate	8	10.26
Total	78	100

Most participants (80.77%) were college graduates, and 51.28% had served for one to four years.

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Table 4
 Years of Service

Years of Service	f	%
3-5 months	6	7.69
6-11 months	18	23.08
1-4 years	40	51.28
5 years and above	14	17.95
Total	78	100

The largest proportion (43.59%) earned between ₱12,082 and ₱24,164 monthly, indicating a predominantly low-income group.

Table 5
 Monthly Income

Monthly Income	TOTAL	
	f	%
Middle Middle Income (Between ₱84,574.00 to ₱48,328.00)	3	3.85
Lower Middle Income (Between ₱48,328.00 to ₱24,164.00.00)	14	17.95
Low Income Class (Between ₱24,164.00 to ₱12,082.00)	34	43.59
Poor (Less than ₱12,082.00)	27	34.62
Total	78	100

These findings suggest that regular LGU employees in Kawayan are relatively young, educated, and financially constrained an important context for interpreting financial literacy results. Results indicated that the participants possessed strong foundational financial knowledge.

Approximately 73% strongly agreed that they understood the concept of budgeting, while 44% strongly agreed that they understood financial planning. However, only 23% strongly agreed that they understood insurance and risk management. Understanding of tax implications and investment principles was also relatively weak.

These findings confirm that the participants are competent in basic money management but less informed about advanced financial concepts, a pattern consistent with the observations of Lusardi and Mitchell (2014). The participants demonstrated positive financial attitudes. About 67% strongly valued saving money, and 60% reported focusing on needs rather than wants. The participants generally believed in the importance of financial planning and disciplined spending.

Around **45% of participants admitted to occasionally borrowing from co-workers**, reflecting reliance on informal credit due to financial constraints despite awareness of proper money management. The findings showed **moderate financial behavior**, with **51% prioritizing debt repayment** and **78% paying bills on time**, demonstrating responsibility in meeting short-term obligations. However, only **18% had an emergency fund** and **14% engaged in investments**, revealing limited engagement in long-term financial planning. These results suggest that while LGU employees practice basic financial discipline, **income limitations and immediate financial needs** hinder their ability to build savings or pursue long-term financial security.

Table 6
Frequency Distribution of Scores for Knowledge, Attitude, and Behavior Questions

<i>Statements</i>	5		4		3		2		1		TOTAL	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
I. Financial Knowledge												
1. I understand what budget is.	57	73	19	24	2	2.6	0	0	0	0	78	100
2. I know how to manage debts.	36	46	31	40	11	14	0	0	0	0	78	100
3. I understand the importance of financial planning.	34	44	32	41	11	14	0	0	1	1.3	78	100
4. I understand the basics of saving and investing.	31	40	39	50	6	7.7	2	2.6	0	0	78	100
5. I understand the importance of insurance and risk management.	18	23	44	56	10	13	4	5.1	2	2.6	78	100
6. I understand the tax implications of my income and benefits.	21	27	42	54	10	13	2	2.6	3	3.8	78	100
TOTAL	33	42	35	44	8.3	11	1.3	1.7	1	1.3	78	100
II. Financial Attitude												
1. I value saving money.	52	67	17	22	7	9	2	2.6	0	0	78	100
2. I focus on spending on my needs rather than on my wants.	47	60	21	27	8	10	2	2.6	0	0	78	100
3. I do borrow money from my co-workers.	35	45	23	29	11	14	6	7.7	3	3.8	78	100
4. I believe it's important to plan for unexpected expenses.	31	40	35	45	5	6.4	2	2.6	5	6.4	78	100
5. It is important to think and plan on my expenses.	33	42	35	45	4	5.1	1	1.3	5	6.4	78	100
TOTAL	40	51	26	34	7	9	2.6	3.3	2.6	3.3	78	100
III. Financial Behavior												
1. I like to pay off debts.	40	51	28	36	4	5.1	2	2.6	4	5.1	78	100
2. I do not stick on only one source of income.	30	38	35	45	5	6.4	6	7.7	2	2.6	78	100
3. I pay my bills on time and avoid late fees.	26	33	35	45	11	14	5	6.4	1	1.3	78	100
4. I have an emergency fund to cover unexpected expenses.	14	18	24	31	26	33	11	14	3	3.8	78	100
5. I have an investment plan.	11	14	23	29	25	32	13	17	6	7.7	78	100
6. I regularly review my financial goals and adjust my plans as needed.	12	15	36	46	15	19	10	13	5	6.4	78	100
TOTAL	22	28	30	39	14	18	7.8	10	3.5	4.5	78	100

Participants experienced difficulty managing salaries amid rising prices, using budgeting mainly for survival. Common financial burdens included medical emergencies, tuition fees, and household repairs, often resulting in reliance on loans or borrowing during crises. Support from family, peers, and cooperatives reflected Filipino mutual aid values but also led to recurring debt and financial vulnerability (OECD, 2016; Lusardi, Schneider, & Tufano, 2011; Bernheim, 1998; Lusardi & Tufano, 2015).

Income level emerged as the most influential variable affecting financial behavior. Participants in higher income brackets demonstrated stronger saving habits and debt management, while those in lower income categories struggled to balance daily expenses and long-term financial goals. This supports OECD (2016) and Lusardi (2019), who found that income inequality directly impacts financial competence.

Explore the challenges on financial literacy of regular LGU Employees.

Figure 2.

Challenges faced about Financial Literacy

Thematic Map of the

The qualitative data reinforced the quantitative results, highlighting that income insufficiency, unexpected expenses, and reliance on borrowing serve as barriers to financial stability. While the participants displayed awareness of responsible financial behavior, limited economic capacity prevented consistent application.

Overall, the study emphasizes that financial literacy among LGU employees extends beyond personal competence. Institutional involvement is necessary to foster financial education and sustainability. The authors recommend that LGUs integrate financial management seminars, savings programs, and cooperative-based financial planning sessions into their employee development initiatives. Such interventions can transform financial literacy from a personal responsibility into an organizational culture, promoting not only individual welfare but also institutional integrity and community resilience.

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